

EXPLORING THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ACUMEN OF YOUNG WOMEN START-UP ENTREPRENEURS IN CALAMBA CITY, LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the experiences of young women managing startups in Calamba City, Laguna. It sought to understand their backgrounds, the challenges they face, the opportunities they see, and the specific training they need. Ultimately, the goal is to develop a customized training program that empowers their entrepreneurial ventures. The researcher explored this phenomenon through a qualitative research method. The target population for this study was composed of young women entrepreneurs. The study sample consisted of eight (8) participants between the ages of 18 and 35. The key instrument of data collection in the study was semi-structured interviews. The researcher subsequently analyzed the collected data through thematic analysis. The findings reveal a common thread of innovativeness and resilience among these women. Despite facing hurdles like limited access to capital, difficulty adapting to the market, competition, operational challenges, and societal biases, many startups demonstrate promising performance and significant growth potential. The study also identified opportunities such as expanding market reach and room for substantial business expansion. The young women entrepreneurs expressed a strong desire for training programs tailored to their needs. They emphasized the importance of hands-on learning methods like workshops, group discussions, case studies, and individual mentorship to support their development. This research led to the creation of a comprehensive training plan that addresses the identified skill gaps. To further support the participants, the program will be complemented by a mentorship initiative. This comprehensive approach aims to equip young women entrepreneurs with the knowledge and skills they need to navigate the complexities of entrepreneurship, ultimately contributing to the growth and sustainability of their businesses in the competitive landscape.

Keywords: *young women entrepreneurs, start-up businesses, Calamba City, Laguna, opportunities and challenges, tailored training plan*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

Many Filipinos are drawn to starting their own businesses, especially those who come from ordinary backgrounds and want to succeed despite challenges. These stories inspire countless others to become entrepreneurs for financial freedom. For many Filipinos, becoming an entrepreneur is a way to be independent, create new things, and prosper. A recent survey showed a strong entrepreneurial spirit among Filipinos, with 78% wanting to start their own businesses for financial reasons and to support themselves (Monzon, 2023).

Starting a business in the Philippines is not easy. There can be many challenges, from money problems to personal difficulties (Velasco et al., 2016). While many Filipinos believe they can be entrepreneurs, many don't have formal training. This highlights the need for programs to help and develop entrepreneurial skills (Velasco et al., 2016). Younger Filipinos, particularly Generation Z, are entering the entrepreneurial space with a fresh perspective. Their digital fluency, openness to new ideas, and comfort with risk-taking are fueling a new wave of business ventures (MoneySense, 2023). Women are increasingly taking the leap into entrepreneurship, demonstrating confidence in their abilities to launch and run successful businesses (Velasco et al., 2016).

In Calamba City, Laguna, young women entrepreneurs have exhibited remarkable resilience and adaptability, leveraging their entrepreneurial acumen to capitalize on emerging trends and meet evolving consumer demands. Supported by collaborative networks offering mentorship and funding avenues, these entrepreneurs have thrived in the face of adversity. The study of young women entrepreneurs holds a profound fascination for me, driven by a deep sense of admiration for their achievements. Their success stories evoke within me a desire to emulate their path in the future.

Young women entrepreneurs are making a big difference in the society. Their innovative ideas, business ventures, and unwavering dedication hold the potential to drive economic growth, spur technological advancements, and foster social progress. Moreover, the positive ripple effects of their entrepreneurial endeavors extend beyond economic realms, touching the lives of individuals within their communities. Motivated by the growing presence of young women in start-up entrepreneurship and a commitment to promoting diversity in the entrepreneurial landscape, the study embarked on a journey to explore the experiences of a select group of young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna.

Research Objectives

Given the increasing number of young women in start-up entrepreneurship, the central aim of this study was to answer this question: What are the perspectives of these young women on managing start-up businesses?

The study sought to answer the following:

1. To determine the profile of start-up entrepreneurs in terms of:
 - a. Entrepreneurial traits
 - b. Existing operations management practices
 - c. Current business performance
2. To describe the opportunities and challenges encountered by selected start-ups owned by young women in Calamba City, Laguna;
3. To identify specific training needs that are relevant to young women entrepreneurs, especially those in the early stage of sustaining their businesses; and
4. To develop a training plan that addresses the challenges and opportunities faced by young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna.

Framework Of the Study

Theoretical Perspectives

The study was anchored on the following theories: Entrepreneurial Trait Theory, Resource-Based Theory, and Opportunity-Based Theory. These theories offer valuable insights into understanding oneself, identifying growth strategies, and improving business performance. The conceptual framework for this study incorporates various variables reflecting the objectives and theoretical foundations.

Firstly, the **Entrepreneurial Trait Theory** guides the examination of entrepreneurial traits such as risk-taking propensity, innovation, proactiveness, and resilience among start-up entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna. These traits are crucial in shaping individuals' propensity to engage in entrepreneurial activities and influence their approach to business management.

Secondly, the **Resource-Based Theory** is reflected in the consideration of existing operations management practices, including production planning, inventory management, quality control, and logistics. This theory emphasizes the significance of internal resources and capabilities in gaining competitive advantage, highlighting the importance of operational efficiencies in start-up success.

Thirdly, the **Opportunity-Based Theory** informs the exploration of opportunities and challenges encountered by young women-owned start-ups in the area. Opportunities such as market gaps, emerging trends, and external environmental factors are examined alongside challenges such as barriers, obstacles, and risks, reflecting the dynamic interplay between external factors and entrepreneurial actions.

By integrating these theoretical foundations into the conceptual framework, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape in Calamba City, Laguna, and identified specific training needs relevant to young women entrepreneurs in the early stages of sustaining their businesses to achieve growth.

The assessment of entrepreneurial learning among young women start-up entrepreneurs essentially serves as the bridge between understanding the current knowledge and skills possessed by these entrepreneurs to be able to design a targeted training program that can enhance their capabilities further. This strategic approach ensures that the training program directly addresses their learning gaps and equips them with practical tools and knowledge essential for success in their entrepreneurial endeavors.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Philosophical Lens

Interpretivism asserts that reality is subjective, varied, and socially constructed, emphasizing that understanding someone's reality requires examining their unique experiences, shaped by historical and social perspectives. In studying start-up entrepreneurs, interpretive techniques are employed to characterize participants' profiles, focusing on their lived experiences, perceptions, and interpretations rather than solely on quantifiable data or objective realities. This approach is vital in exploring the complexities of entrepreneurial behavior, decision-making, and responses to challenges and opportunities, recognizing that these actions are influenced by individual perceptions and motivations.

For example, in a study of young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna,

interpretivism would enable researchers to delve into how these entrepreneurs perceive and navigate the start-up landscape, uncovering insights into their traits, practices, and the contextual factors impacting their businesses. By embracing interpretivism's qualitative nature, using methods such as interviews and document analysis, researchers can capture the depth and intricacies of entrepreneurial experiences, offering valuable insights for both theory and practical support in fostering start-up success.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused on exploring the experiences of young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna through a qualitative research method such as interviews. While the qualitative approach provided rich insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by these entrepreneurs, the sample size was limited to eight participants aged between 18 and 35. This narrow focus may restrict the generalizability of the findings to a broader population of young entrepreneurs in the area.

Additionally, the study aimed to provide in-depth insights rather than statistical generalizations, emphasizing the need for further research to encompass a more diverse range of perspectives and experiences. Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights and a foundation for future exploration and support for women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna.

Operational Definition of Terms

Start-up Entrepreneurship. As used in the study, it refers to business ventures which just opened and established with the goal of expansion and growth in Calamba City.

Start-up Entrepreneurs. They refer to those individuals who just established a business in Calamba City and are on the process of knowledge acquisition and orientation as far as business enterprise is concerned.

Training Program. This refers to the designed output that addresses training needs of start-up entrepreneurs in their business operations.

Women Entrepreneurship. This encompasses the activities that women entrepreneurs in Calamba City undertake from conceptualizing the business, establishing and coordinating its operations, mobilizing and managing resources, assuming risks, and navigating the economic uncertainties inherent in its operation.

Young Entrepreneurs. These are young adults in Calamba City, Laguna whose age ranges from 18-35 years old who initiated start-up businesses.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative study utilized a phenomenological design to explore the

experiences of eight young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, Laguna. The aim was to gain insights into their entrepreneurial profiles, challenges, and training needs.

Research Setting

The study was conducted in Calamba City, Laguna, known for its growing start-up ecosystem and industrial presence within the CALABARZON region.

Participants

Purposive sampling was employed to select eight young women entrepreneurs aged 18 to 35, operating start-up businesses in Calamba City.

Instrumentation

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using an interview guide to collect data on entrepreneurial traits, operational challenges, and training needs.

Data Construction and Analysis

During the interviews, key terms were clarified to ensure participant understanding. Thematic analysis was then applied to the collected data to identify recurring patterns and themes related to the research objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Start-Up Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurial Traits

The entrepreneurial traits and skills identified by the participants highlight key factors that contribute to entrepreneurial success in various industries. Their insights resonate with established concepts in entrepreneurship literature and reflect broader trends observed in entrepreneurial studies. Based on the themes that surfaced, the participants exhibited **innovativeness** and **resilience**. They mentioned words and phrases like **everything is unique, creative, and we always find ways to improve them**. Their focus on innovation and customer connection aligns with findings by Baron and Tang (2011), which highlight creativity as a critical factor for entrepreneurial success, particularly in consumer-centric industries. Many highlighted their ability to persevere through challenges and pivot their business strategies in response to changing circumstances. The words and phrases they frequently used were **flexible, adaptable, ability to adapt and persevere, and I don't know when to give up**. This is a critical attribute in entrepreneurship, as indicated by Bullough et al. (2014), who discuss the importance of resilience in navigating business challenges. Their emphasis on adaptability and perseverance is key to sustaining and growing a business in a

competitive market. The emphasis on not giving up and facing challenges head-on is indicative of the grit and resilience necessary for long-term success in entrepreneurship.

Operational Practices

The operational practices of the start-up ventures varied, but common strategies included leveraging digital platforms for marketing and sales, fostering customer relationships through personalized experiences, and implementing agile decision-making processes. In exploring the operational practices of various entrepreneurs, it becomes evident that customer service is foundational to their business strategies which stemmed to the key theme **establishing rapport with the customers**. The phrases used were **I talk to people, I take care of them, they become our friends, we get closer, and I listen to them**. Key Informant 5 even highlighted focusing on active listening and accepting feedback as key components of exceptional customer service. She believes that understanding and responding to customer needs are paramount for long-term success, echoing the principles of customer relationship management. She states, “Yes... *accepting feedback, I think. That’s a skill that an owner should have.*” This aligns with the customer-oriented strategy in business, which underscores the importance of understanding and responding to customer needs, a concept widely explored in customer relationship management literature (Payne and Frow, 2013).

Business Performance

Despite facing initial hurdles, the majority of participants reported positive business performance indicators, such as revenue growth, customer acquisition, and brand recognition. The common theme that surfaced among the participants was **rapid capital recovery**. They uttered phrases such as **we’re doing well, quick return on investment, exponential growth, very good performance, above expectations, huge returns, fast recoup of investment, it’s going well, and exceeded my expectations**. These businesses were established during the pandemic and such growth trajectory in the post-pandemic market is a testament to the businesses’ ability to adapt and meet evolving customer needs. The participants’ aspiration to continue this adaptive approach aligns with the strategic agility concept, which is essential for businesses to thrive in dynamic environments, as discussed by Doz and Kosonen (2010). The current business performance and future aspirations of these entrepreneurs reflect a dynamic and forward-looking approach in their respective fields. Each entrepreneur exhibits a unique perspective on business growth, operational efficiency, and customer engagement, which are fundamental components of successful business strategies. These statements indicate that the businesses mentioned are thriving, exceeding expectations, and maintaining financial stability, reflecting positive outcomes and achievements in their operations.

Opportunities and Challenges Encountered by Young Women Start-Up Entrepreneurs

Opportunities

The biggest opportunities identified by these entrepreneurs in the Calamba City market reflect their understanding of market trends, customer preferences, and the importance of strategic expansion and innovation. Based on the themes that surfaced, the participants identified opportunities such as **expanding market reach** and **business expansion**. They mentioned phrases like **to expand and reach more audiences**, **audience extension**, and **to reach a wider audience**. Most participants highlighted leveraging social media to reach a wider audience. This approach reflects the increasing importance of digital marketing and e-commerce in modern business strategies (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Moreover, Key Informant 2 underscored the importance of an online presence for business expansion. This reflects the strategic importance of digital platforms in expanding market reach and enhancing customer engagement (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). They often used words and phrases such as **branch out to new locations**, **to be able to franchise**, and **franchising**. Franchising emerged as a prominent code, with several key informants recognizing it as a viable strategy for business growth. Franchising provides a structured way of expanding while mitigating risks, a strategy well-regarded in entrepreneurial literature (Segreto, 2022).

Challenges

The main challenges faced by these young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, along with societal and cultural factors impacting their experiences, reflect a blend of external market conditions and internal business dynamics. Based on the accounts of the participants, the emerging themes were **dealing with business competitors** and **handling common business scams**. These challenges underscore the importance of market understanding, adaptability, and effective business management in the entrepreneurial landscape. The codes generated were **understanding customers**, **identifying customer preferences**, **imitative strategy**, **affordable pricing**, **e-commerce fraudsters**, and **advance-fee fraud**. Key Informant 3 highlights the challenge of introducing a unique cuisine to a market that may be unfamiliar with it. She focuses on expanding her restaurant by opening more branches, intending to blend Vietnamese and Filipino tastes. However, her goal highlights the challenge of maintaining authenticity while adapting to local tastes, a concept supported by the localization strategy in international business (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Additionally, the quote: *“So far, there are those who want to imitate us. Because even our logo has been copied.”* suggests a cultural factor where copying successful businesses is seen as a viable strategy. This can be discouraging for young entrepreneurs who invest in creating unique brands and menus. Key Informant 4 addresses the challenges of stiff competition and managing fluctuating customer tastes. This reflects the dynamic nature of the marketplace and the need for continuous innovation and adaptability. Lastly, Key Informant 7 shared a clear encounter with unreliable suppliers which underscores the operational challenges many entrepreneurs face, resonating with the operational risk management strategies

discussed by Brigham and Ehrhardt (2013). Her proactive strategy of switching suppliers and maintaining a positive outlook exemplifies the resilience and adaptive problem-solving skills essential for entrepreneurs, as discussed by Bullough et al. (2014).

Training Needs That Are Relevant to Young Women Start-Up Entrepreneurs

Based on participants' feedback, key support methods identified were **business support groups, awareness campaigns for startups, workshops, and mentorship**. These entrepreneurs seek tailored training programs focusing on crucial areas like financial management, marketing, and networking. Mentorship and funding access were highlighted as critical resources for business growth and sustainability. Key Informant 5 emphasized the value of collaborative marketing efforts within women's groups to enhance business influence. The importance of experiential learning through workshops and mentorship programs was underscored by Key Informant 1 and Key Informant 3, emphasizing practical knowledge and continuous support for skill development and company expansion.

Research supports the effectiveness of experiential learning methods like workshops and mentorship in fostering entrepreneurial competencies and venture success, enhancing problem-solving skills, creativity, and adaptability, and fostering a sense of community among entrepreneurs. Integrating these methods into training programs can enhance support initiatives for women entrepreneurs.

Table 1. Training Plan for Young Women Entrepreneurs

Training Module	Objectives	Content	Methodology	Duration
1. Entrepreneurial Mindset and Resilience	Develop a growth mindset, resilience, and adaptability to overcome challenges in the entrepreneurial journey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of a growth mindset and resilience Identifying personal strengths and areas for improvement Developing strategies for coping with challenges and setbacks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive workshops Group discussions Personal reflection exercises 	4 hours

Training Module	Objectives	Content	Methodology	Duration
2. Market Research and Analysis	Conduct market research, analyze market trends, and identify opportunities for business growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of market research Learning techniques for conducting market research and analysis Identifying market opportunities and threats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures Case studies Group projects 	6 hours
3. Financial Management for Entrepreneurs	Manage finances, budgeting, and financial planning for business success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding financial statements and reports Developing a financial plan Managing cash flow and budgeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures Group discussions Practical exercises 	6 hours
4. Marketing and Branding Strategies	Develop marketing and branding strategies to reach a wider audience and increase business visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of branding and marketing Developing a marketing plan Utilizing social media and online platforms for marketing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures Group discussions Practical exercises 	6 hours
5. Business Strategy and Planning	Learn how to develop a strategic plan for business growth and expansion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of strategic planning Developing a strategic plan for business growth Identifying key performance indicators and monitoring progress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures Group discussions Practical exercises 	6 hours
6. Daily Business Operations	Learn how to manage daily business operations, including administrative tasks, customer service, and HR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the importance of daily business operations Learning techniques for managing administrative tasks, customer service, and HR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures Group discussions Practical exercises 	6 hours

Training Module	Objectives	Content	Methodology	Duration
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizing technology and tools for efficient business operations 		
7. Passion and Personal Interest in Business	Explore how to leverage passion and personal interests in business to drive motivation and success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying personal passions and interests Aligning business ideas with personal interests Harnessing passion for business growth and sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-assessment exercises Case studies Group discussions 	4 hours
8. Mentorship Program	Provide mentorship opportunities for young women entrepreneurs to receive personalized guidance and support from experienced entrepreneurs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pairing young women entrepreneurs with experienced mentors Providing regular check-ins and feedback sessions Giving practical guidance and support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One-on-one mentorship Group discussions Practical exercises 	12 hours (over 3 months)

The training plan is designed to provide young women entrepreneurs with the skills, knowledge, and support they need to succeed in their entrepreneurial journey. The training modules are based on the themes and codes identified from the key informants' statements. The training plan is designed to be flexible and adaptable, allowing for individualized learning and growth. The training modules can be customized to meet the specific needs and goals of each young woman entrepreneur, ensuring that they receive the support and guidance they need to thrive in their business ventures.

Summary of Findings

- 1. Profile of Start-up Entrepreneurs:** Young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City exhibited traits of innovativeness and resilience, showcasing their ability to navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities in the entrepreneurial landscape. Their diverse operational practices reflected a blend of traditional methods and technological advancements, highlighting their adaptability and strategic approach to business management.

2. **Opportunities and Challenges Encountered by Start-ups:** The entrepreneurs identified opportunities such as expanding market reach, leveraging social media for audience engagement, and exploring franchising as a growth strategy. Challenges included competition, business scams, and societal biases, emphasizing the importance of market understanding, adaptability, and effective business management in their entrepreneurial journey.
3. **Training Needs of Young Women Entrepreneurs:** The study underscored the training needs of young women entrepreneurs, emphasizing the necessity for tailored programs in financial management, marketing strategies, networking skills, mentorship, and funding access. Participants highlighted the value of hands-on learning methods like workshops, group discussions, case studies, and individual mentorship to enhance their entrepreneurial capabilities and support their business development.
4. **Development of a Training Plan:** A comprehensive training plan has been created for young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, addressing their specific needs through modules on financial management, marketing, and personal interests. The program utilizes diverse methodologies to maximize effectiveness, considering time constraints and aiming to equip participants with the knowledge and skills for entrepreneurial success.

Conclusions

1. Young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City exhibit innovativeness and resilience indicating a promising entrepreneurial landscape in the region. Many start-ups have expanded successfully, demonstrating their growth potential despite operational management differences.
2. Young women entrepreneurs confront hurdles such as limited financial access, market adaptability, competitiveness, operational issues, and societal biases, despite opportunities like market demand for distinctive products/services and growth potential. Creating a helpful entrepreneurial environment requires addressing these difficulties.
3. The demand for customized training programs highlights the need to address skill gaps in financial management, marketing, networking, mentorship, and funding for young women entrepreneurs. They enjoy hands-on learning through workshops, group discussions, case studies, and mentorship, which can help them navigate entrepreneurship.
4. A customized training strategy for young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City is crucial for bridging skill shortages and promoting growth and sustainability. The training program includes modules on entrepreneurial mindset, market research, financial management, marketing strategies, business planning, daily operations, and leveraging personal interests, as well as a mentorship program. Multiple

methods accommodate diverse learning styles and time restrictions for optimal effectiveness and relevance.

Recommendations

This study provides valuable insights into young women entrepreneurs in Calamba City, but there's an opportunity to delve deeper and address these identified gaps through the following recommendations: **continuous learning opportunities, networking and collaboration, feedback and evaluation mechanisms, long-term career development plans, and future research.** The enhancement of women's entrepreneurship in Calamba City, Laguna requires a multifaceted approach involving education, practical support, research, and policy changes. By addressing these recommendations, there is potential to not only support women entrepreneurs but also to contribute to economic development and gender equality.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

High ethical standards were maintained throughout the duration of the study. To ensure strict adherence to ethical considerations, the following measures were implemented:

- Informed consent and assent were obtained from the respondents by clearly presenting to them their role in participating and allowing them to voluntarily sign the informed consent and assent form;
- The risk of harm to respondents was minimized by strictly adhering to safety protocols against the transmission of COVID-19 and other viruses;
- The confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were safeguarded by preventing unauthorized access to their personal information and the collected responses. Therefore, real names were not revealed for security and privacy of the companies used;
- The research was conducted truthfully and honestly with the sole objective of doing research and without intending to deceive any respondents; and
- The respondents were afforded the right and freedom to withdraw from participating in the study if they feel uncomfortable or unwilling to continue.

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